

DEVELOPING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LEARNING FOR LAZY LEARNERS IN NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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In today's globalization environment, the demands placed on the education system are becoming increasingly complex. Society needs individuals who can think independently, communicate, and constantly develop their knowledge. Therefore, the education system is faced with the task of not only imparting knowledge, but also of engaging students in learning and forming their internal motivation. The problem of passive learners remains particularly relevant in the teaching of the native language in secondary schools.

The native language is a subject that plays an important role in the formation of individual thinking. Through this subject, students learn speech culture, logical thinking, and fluent expression of their thoughts. However, in practice, many students do not have sufficient knowledge in this subject. The reasons for this are various: low motivation, psychological barriers, one-sidedness of traditional teaching methods, etc. The problem of working with passive learners remains particularly relevant in the process of teaching the native language. Such students are often passive during the lesson, hesitate to answer questions, find it difficult to express their opinions freely, and as a result, they acquire knowledge superficially. This situation negatively affects the quality of education.

The mother tongue lesson is not limited to teaching grammatical rules, but also involves the development of students' speech culture, thinking and communication competencies. Therefore, the use of interactive methods within this subject is an important means of increasing students' interest in the lesson, involving them in active learning, and increasing the effectiveness of mastering.[5]

This thesis discusses the issue of activating passive learners in native language lessons through interactive methods and increasing their effectiveness in mastering lessons.

Passive learners are students who have not sufficiently mastered knowledge, skills and competencies, and have a weak attitude towards learning. They often do not actively participate in the lesson process, hesitate to answer questions, make mistakes in written work and are afraid of evaluation. As a result, they lose self-confidence and become even more passive.

From a psychological point of view, such students have low self-esteem, fear of failure and social withdrawal. Therefore, an individual approach to them is important.

Motivation is an internal force that encourages a person to act. A student who is not motivated to learn perceives knowledge as an obligation. Interactive methods involve the student in an active process and awaken his internal need.

Interactive methods are methods based on cooperative learning, in which the teacher acts as a guide and the student is an active participant.

Methods such as brainstorming, cluster, insert, role-playing, debate, group work increase the speech activity of students.

As a result of interactive methods, students' interest in the lesson increases, independent thinking develops, and the level of mastery increases.[3]

Proving the effectiveness of interactive methods with examples

Example 1: “Brainstorming” method

Situation: The topic “Word Groups” is being studied in a 6th grade native language lesson. Students who are passive learners usually do not answer questions.

Interactive approach:

The teacher asks a question at the beginning of the lesson:

“What function do words perform in speech?”

Each student is required to express at least one thought, and is not criticized for mistakes.

Result: Students who were previously silent also express their thoughts and feel free. The topic is understandable to everyone at the initial level. This attracts passive learners to active learning.

Example 2: “Role Playing” method

Situation: The topic “Formal and Informal Speech” is being studied.

Interactive approach:

Students are given a situation:

one writes an application to the school principal;

one writes a message to a friend.

They demonstrate the type of speech in practice.

Result: Students learn the rule not by memorizing it, but by applying it. The passive learner also actively participates and the topic is reinforced.

Example 3: Studying a text using the “Insert” method

Situation: Students read the text without understanding it.

Interactive approach:

Marks are put:

✓ I know

? I didn't understand

new information

Result: The student realizes what he or she has understood. This develops the skill of reflection.

Example 4: Working in a group. The passive learner is placed in a group with a strong learner, and learning takes place in collaboration.

These examples prove that interactive methods:

turn the student into an active participant;

reduces fear;

ensures conscious assimilation of knowledge.[4]

Thus, interactive methods are a real and proven pedagogical tool for increasing the cognitive efficiency of passive learners.

In conclusion, the use of interactive methods in native language lessons can activate passive learners, improve their knowledge is an important condition for increasing the effectiveness of language acquisition. These methods fundamentally change the student's attitude to the learning process, turning him from a passive listener into an active participant. As a result, students learn to freely express their opinions, participate in discussions, and independently enrich their knowledge.

Interactive approaches reduce the psychological barriers that exist in passive learners, in particular, fear of mistakes, self-doubt, and passivity. The friendly and supportive environment created during the lesson increases the students' speech activity and serves to consciously master language material.

Interactive methods also form students' internal motivation for learning, that is, they begin to acquire knowledge not only for the sake of grades, but based on the need to know. As a result, the overall level of students' mastery increases, and the quality of teaching the subject of their native language improves.

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